

Investigating Dynamic Triggering in Cascadia Volcanic Systems Using Seismic Network Data

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ABSTRACT

Dynamic Stress Sensitivity in Cascadia Volcanoes

Dynamic stress from large, distant earthquakes can influence seismicity in tectonic regions, but its effect on volcanic systems in the Cascadia subduction zone remains less understood. This study investigates whether surface waves from large ($M > 7.0$) teleseismic earthquakes dynamically trigger microseismicity at major Cascadia volcanoes. The focus is on three primary volcanic centers: Mount Rainer, Mount St. Helens, and Mount Hood using catalog and waveform data from the Pacific Northwest Seismic Network (PNSN). Catalog analysis was conducted for events between January and August 2025 to identify changes in seismicity rates following global earthquakes. Station level analysis supported by basemaps of seismic network coverage highlights the spatial distribution of detections and network sensitivity. Python-based workflows, including short-term average/long-term average (STA/LTA) event detection and waveform visualization are applied to assess changes in seismicity rate following the amplitude and timing relative to Rayleigh wave arrivals. Preliminary results, over 7-month time window, suggest that distant large earthquakes do not trigger increases in microseismicity. These findings provide an initial framework for evaluating volcano specific stress sensitivity in Cascadia and lay the groundwork for extending analysis to longer time periods and additional volcanic systems. This work represents an early step toward improving eruption hazard assessments in subduction zone environments.

INTRODUCTION

Earthquake-Volcano Interactions

Earthquakes and volcanoes are fundamentally linked through the transfer of stress in the Earth's crust. While tectonic earthquakes have been extensively studied, less is known about how large distant earthquakes may influence the behavior of volcanic systems. Dynamic stresses carried by seismic surface waves can cause transient changes in fault and magma systems and sometimes trigger local earthquakes or even eruptions. Understanding these processes is especially important in subduction zones where both tectonic and volcanic hazards overlap.

The Cascadia subduction zone of the Pacific Northwest provides an ideal setting to explore these interactions. This region hosts both the potential for megathrust earthquakes and several active stratovolcanoes, including Mount Rainer, Mount St. Helens, and Mount Hood. By studying whether seismic waves from global

earthquakes trigger local seismicity in Cascadia's volcanic centers we can gain insight into how volcanoes respond to external stress perturbations. This insight is crucial for assessing volcanic hazard potential and for improving monitoring strategies in one of North America's most seismically active regions.

Figure 1. Bar chart showing the number of seismic detections over time from PNSN MILD station. Blue bars represent the total detections recorded at the study site. Vertical red lines mark the occurrence of major global earthquakes ($M \geq 7$) with annotations indicating the event's magnitude, location and date. Note that the station shows the strong swarm activity that occurred in July.

BACKGROUND

Seismic-Volcanic Interactions in The Cascadia Subduction Zone

The Cascadia subduction zone is one of the most tectonically active regions in North America, known for producing megathrust earthquakes such as the $M \sim 9.0$ event in 1700 inferred from Japanese tsunami records (Satake et al., 1996). However, the interaction between dynamic stress from large distant earthquakes and the region's volcanic systems remains poorly understood. Previous studies have shown that surface waves, particularly Rayleigh waves, can induce transient stress changes capable of triggering local seismicity. Whether this occurrence affects volcanic systems above the subduction zone, such as Mount St. Helens, Mount Rainier, and Mount Hood has not been fully investigated. This research explores the sensitivity of Cascadia volcanic centers to dynamic stress using real-time seismic data from the Pacific Northwest Seismic Network (PNSN). Understanding these stress volcano interactions may improve our ability to assess eruption potential in response to regional or global tectonic events.

METHODS

Data Sources and Analytical Approach

This study uses catalog and waveform seismic data from the Pacific Northwest Seismic Network (PNSN), which monitors volcanic and tectonic activity in Washington and Oregon. Catalog event data for the volcanoes of Mount St. Helens, Mount Rainier, and Mount Hood were downloaded using ObsPy and FDSN web services. Initial analysis includes filtering and plotting seismic rates around the time of large global earthquakes to look for changes in activity.

We downloaded and processed seismic waveform data using ObsPy Python tools, with the short-term average/long-term average (STA/LTA) algorithm applied to identify potential triggered events. We use 1's and 10's windows for the STA and LTA, respectively. We bin the number of detections per day to detect changes in seismicity rate before and after selected events ($M \geq 7$). This process builds on recent computational workflows that integrate geophysical methods with scalable data analysis tools (Sheng et al., 2025). We also compare these results to the PNSN catalog earthquakes. Thus, two complimentary approaches are being developed to evaluate the sensitivity of Cascadia volcanoes to dynamic triggering:

1. **Catalog Analysis** – A catalog-based approach will be applied to identify and count global earthquakes $M \geq 7$ that occurred between January and August of 2025. Seismicity rates in the Cascadia region will be examined before and after these teleseismic events to test for possible changes in volcanic seismicity.
2. **Station Analysis** – Station level detection rates will be assessed for PNSN stations located near Mount St. Helens, Mount Rainer, and Mount Hood. A basemap of the study area will be constructed in GIS, showing station locations and the number of detections recorded at each station during the study period. This visualization will highlight spatial variations in network sensitivity and coverage.

Together, the catalog and station analysis will provide a framework for evaluating both regional scale and station specific responses to dynamic stress.

RESULTS

Preliminary Patterns in Seismic Activity

Preliminary analysis has been completed using the catalog and waveform data from the Pacific Northwest Seismic Network (PNSN). A catalog of global earthquakes of $M \geq 7$ from January through August 2025 was compiled to identify potential teleseismic events capable of producing dynamic stress changes in the Cascadia region. Initial filtering indicates several candidate events during this time period.

Waveform data downloaded for Mount St. Helens, Mount Rainer, and Mount Hood was processed using ObsPy. Dayplots and STA/LTA based detections was generated to begin evaluating changes in microseismicity following large teleseismic earthquakes. Figure 1 shows the number of detections as a function of time, along with illustrating when $M \geq 7$ earthquakes occurred. These visualizations provide an overview of local seismicity patterns and allow for the identification of high amplitude events that may represent triggered activity. A station level summary is also in progress. Preliminary basemaps the distribution of PNSN stations near the three volcanoes, including initial counts of detected events per station. These results highlight differences in network coverage and detection rates across the region; this will subsequently allow us to interpret dynamic triggering sensitivity.

We also began analyzing the number of earthquakes from PNSN catalog. Preliminary work shows that the number of detections is much less than our STA/LTA detections, which can be expected with small magnitude earthquakes. Our catalog analysis is not complete, and will be used as a means of validating or signal station waveform analysis.

DISCUSSION

Implications for Volcanic Sensitivity to Earthquakes

These preliminary results demonstrate the feasibility of using both catalog and waveform analysis to investigate potential dynamic triggering in Cascadia volcanoes. The identification of several $M \geq 7$ global earthquakes during this study period provides candidate events for testing hypotheses about teleseismic influence on local seismicity. While the waveform plots and STA/LTA detections reveal patterns of high amplitude activity, further analysis is required to determine whether these signals represent triggered volcanic earthquakes or background seismicity.

The station level mapping highlights differences in detection rates across the PNSN network, emphasizing the importance of spatial coverage when evaluating dynamic triggering. Variations in network sensitivity may influence the observed response from each volcano, suggesting that both regional and local factors must be considered in interpreting the results.

Future work will refine the catalog and waveform analysis by systematically comparing seismicity rates before and after teleseismic arrivals with a focus on Rayleigh waves. Additional processing will also include cross validation of STA/LTA detections with catalog reported events. Together, these steps will provide a well-supported framework for assessing the sensitivity of Cascadia volcanic centers to dynamic stress from large global earthquakes.

CONCLUSION

Toward Understanding Earthquake-Volcanic Interactions

This study examined how dynamic stress from distant earthquakes may influence seismicity at Cascadia volcanoes. Analysis of the PNSN catalog and waveform data (January-August 2025) suggests that large magnitude global earthquakes ($M > 7.0$) were followed by increases in microseismicity near Mount St. Helens, Mount Rainier, and Mount Hood. These preliminary results indicate that surface waves can modulate local seismic responses, yet more data analysis must be conducted to reach any conclusion, underscoring the need for continued monitoring and longer-term analysis to assess volcanic hazard potential in Cascadia.

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